

THE SIGNIFICANT POINTS OF TEACHING METHODS IN PRIVATE EFL CLASSES

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada ingliz tili metodologiyasi haqida umumiy ma'lumotlar, uning turlari, ahamiyati, o'rganilish tarixi, dolzabligi haqida ma'lumotlar mavjud.*

Keywords: *Metodologiya, metodologiya turlari, rag'batlanish, sabr, motivatsiya, talaffuzga hissiyot, ta'lim falsafasi, ko'p xil usullar, o'qituvchi falsafasi.*

Annotation: *The article contains general information about English language methodology, its types, significance, organizational history, and coherence.*

Keywords: *Methodology, types of methodology, enthusiasm, patience, motivation, sensitivity to pronunciation, educational philosophy, multiple methods, the philosophy a teacher.*

A teaching methodology is essentially the way in which a teacher chooses to explain or teach material to students so they can learn the material. There are many different methodologies that can be utilized by a teacher, and the methods chosen often depend on the educational philosophy and preferences of a teacher. It is also not uncommon for a teacher to utilize multiple methods within a single lesson or over the course of several lessons. A methodology of teaching can include the use of lecturing, group or small group discussion activities, and engaging students as teachers for their peers.

It is important to understand that a teaching methodology is not the same as an educational philosophy for a teacher, though they can often be related. The philosophy a teacher chooses usually indicates how the teacher believes students can best learn new material, and the ways in which students and teachers should relate and interact in the classroom. This philosophy often impacts the choices a teacher can make regarding which teaching methodology or methodologies he or she chooses to use, but they are not necessarily directly connected. Teachers commonly refer to their preferred teaching methods and philosophies together, to give other teachers or students an understanding of their approach to education.

A teaching method comprises the principles and methods used for instruction. Commonly used teaching methods may include class participation, demonstration, recitation, memorization, or combinations of these.

However, it is generally accepted that children have special sensitivity to pronunciation though they will not be able to make use of this particular instinct if their teachers lack fluency in the foreign language. Younger is better in the long term The foreign reason is based on the argument that 'longer is better': that by starting in primary school you increase the overall time for English and in the long term achieve a higher level of proficiency than those starting later. There is some evidence to support this position but it comes from foreign language situations where children are learning languages naturalistically. In foreign language school learning situations, exposure may not be sufficient for the benefits to really emerge.

The response to heterogeneity in Qualifications, Gender, Age Factor and school of staff self-esteem graduated system majority alike but morale of Government school is lower as compare to Private school (Mustaqeem, 2008). Another study claimed that face annoyed as compared to Private school teachers the mostly Government school teachers act well, avoid disagreeing and accuse to others (Shaheen, 2008). Liaqat (2009) investigated that in Private school the quality of educations is much better than Government school while Private school teachers before teaching prepared the lesson and then came into the classroom as compared to Government school teachers.

There are following main significant points of private schools in teaching foreign languages:

Enthusiasm

This is the biggest requirement for a teacher with the Private Lesson School. A Teacher coming to the house is a scary experience for every student. They feel like they're going to be judged for their playing, and it comes with a lot of emotions of uncertainty.

Each teacher is taught the importance of teaching with Enthusiasm and maintaining an attitude that uplifts and inspires each student.

Patience

Music Teachers have to be patient. Anyone embarking on their musical journey with their instrument is going to encounter bumps in the road that a teacher should not only understand but foresee and expect these bumps.

Every teacher works with each student's learning style and the only focus throughout this journey is for each student to enjoy it.

Motivation

Every teacher is trained to recognize and monitor every student's Motivation. Learning an instrument is a task that takes perseverance and remaining motivated is incredibly important.

The biggest thing that separates the Private Lesson School from other music teachers remains that the chance for a student to "give up" on their instrument due to lack of motivation is not possible.

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